

WHAT DRIVES GREEN PURCHASING BEHAVIOR? INDONESIA CUSTOMERS' EVIDENCES FROM THE PERSPECTIVE OF THEORY OF PLANNED BEHAVIOR (TPB) & SELF-DETERMINATION THEORY (SDT)

KARDISON LUMBAN BATU ¹ and HERSUGONDO ²

^{1,2} Faculty of Economics and Business, Department of Management, Diponegoro University.

Abstract

Current study tried to investigated the antecedents of green purchase intention by integrating the intrinsic motivation and others factors into TPB and further combined with SDT. deploying offline survey through google form during September and October 2023 in Indonesia (represented big cities) and aimed at customers who had purchased green products or had experiences eco-friendly products. As many 400 respondents filled and completed the survey but there were 380 questionnaires were valid for further analysis. found that green purchasing behavior was directly affected by green purchase intention, environment attitude, and intrinsic motivation. Purposive sampling with non-probability sampling and SEM with AMOS 24 deployed for data analysis. Research finding described that Green customer's behavior was affected positively by green purchase intention. Besides, the customer intrinsic motivation also proven as the antecedent of GCB. The intrinsic motivation known as the antecedent for environmental attitude and green purchasing intension. As a consequence, this finding was validated that GPI and EA which reflected by customers acted as the effective indicator for green customer purchase behavior.

Keywords: GPI, Intrinsic Motivation, Green Customer Purchase Behavior.

1. INTRODUCTION

The excess exploitation of natural resources and massive industrialization practices had led to the continuously environmental damage such water resource damage, air pollution and natural disaster (Gutiérrez et al., 2022). Some countries came to realization and started to take action to reduce the negative impact of activation on natural (Donatti et al., 2022). In this phenomenon, current customers had been gradually switched purchase from conservative products into green or environmentally products, the product which prioritized natural resources conservation and low pollution, aligned with the rise of awareness on environmental care (Marcon et al., 2022).

Current shifting is becoming well-known in some countries with dense population. Some Asian countries experienced the rise needs related with green products due to the increase of incomes for expenditures (Dong et al., 2022). Therefore, the needs to explore customers' green purchase intention to trigger the green or organic products foods sales (Sun et al., 2022). With no doubt it has dragged academicians interest to examine the green purchase behavior such as Sun et al. (2022). The study showed the significant function of mediation of proudness and guilty anticipation in the friendly commitment impact on green purchase behavior which is bigger on high level social norm, while Zhang et al., (2023) revealed a& claimed that environment care

and green promotion and branding showed the significant impact on customer friendly behavior. In the other hand, the previous study (Maduku, 2024) had also revealed that the difference between customer positive attitude on green product consumption and purchase behavior, which is often resulted from the lack of customer information on green product. The gaps among this attitude and behavior could hamper the green product market, slow and late response toward the responsible implementation on business environment, and at the last, it could also postpone the continuously development progress (Dhir et al., 2020). Yet, the gap is still remained unknown.

In the other side, the authors have already deployed many modes approaches to investigate the green customer purchase, some of them are, Stimulus Organism Responds (Kuo and Chen, 2023), theory Rationale Attitude (Małecka et al., 2022) and TPB (Ajzen, 1991). Even though current study explored how the external factors affected the individual internal factors and further attitude, SOR itself could not able to examine the tendency of individual voluntary to be engaged in certain attitude (Liu et al., 2023a, 2023b). meanwhile, TRA, which at the very beginning used to estimate customer intention and attitude in daily routines, had been critic due to its narrow perception on rationality. These critical derived from insufficient capability to define the consequences of unreasonable elements and circumstantial in person during the process of managerial (Ozkara and Bagozzi, 2021).

During this condition, TPB is existed as a tool to predict the green customer attitude (Mahardika., 2019). Aligned with TPB, attitude is directly affected by objective which is affected by subjective norm and perceived attitude control (PAC). Academicians have widely admitted the role of mediator in the green inclination to buy to connect the green attitude with real green product purchase. Thus, it became pivotal to raise green customer purchase intention to support the green product sales (Testa et al., 2020). Meanwhile, previous research (Alyahya et al., 2023) showed the higher customer wish to purchase green product when realized that their green behavior.

As a consequence, customer subjective norm played crucial role to predict green purchase attitude. Yet, TPB itself has limitation, one of them are its inability to fully integrated the impact of internal and external motivation on customer green purchase attitude. Thus, many experts underlined the need to widen the model of TPB by adding the personal traits which could affect the customer traits (Kirmani et al., 2023). Yet, only a few literatures such as (Roh et al., 2022) investigated the role of customer attitude on environment in the scope of environmentally friendly.

More recently, the motivation concept and self-destiny determination is more applied in various situation related with green product. According to Self Determination Theory, personal motivation is appeared as a sustainable which reflects the different level of self-determination and showed the different level of external and internal control among human being (Deci and Ryan, 1985). Due to the self-determination motive played crucial positive role within purchase goals, SDT could offer a new-brand perspective to understand the customer incitement related with friendly purchase intention or motivation (Tandon et al., 2020). In accordance with above analysis, current study tried to investigated the predecessors or antecedents of green purchase

intention by consolidating the intrinsic motivation and others factors into TPB and further combined with SDT. Besides, the subjective norm is considered into a model and investigated the moderating role in the influence of motivation on intention and ensure the interaction between two constructs. This articles have many implication as well as theoretical and managerial. In the other sides, enlarge TPB roles with environmental attitude and narrowing the gaps between attitude and behavior. For another benefits, this article offers the guidance for marketing strategic for firms. The rest of articles are set as follows. The section 2 for literature review, part 3 describe the hypotheses development. The 4 part analyzed the methodology, and findings and 5 section. The last part is discussion, limitation and further research.

2. LITERATURES REVIEWED

2.1. Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB)

TPB has been considered as robust theoretical mode to estimate the person attitude due to its capability to recognize and predict wide social attitude coverage (Alzubaidi et al., 2021). This theory was derived from TRA, both agreed that attitude decision was resulted from valid information processed.

In accordance with TPB, the emerged of attitude pretentious by the intention, an establish formed by subjective norm, recognized attitude dominance and behavior. Subjective norm covered double aspects, they are, how far the referential figure significantly supports and against certain attitude and person motivation intensity to obey referential figure (Liu et al., 2023a, 2023b). the point is, subjective norm referred to society point of view on influential person.

Various research had shown the strong correlation among customer attitude, subjective norm, customer intention as well as customer behavior. Based on the investigation on China customer behavior, subjective norm was pinpoint as a significant forecaster (Agag and Colmekcioglu, 2020), While a new research in India revealed that subjective norm as significantly increase domestic customer to revisit green hotel (Haq et al., 2023). Discerned customer's behavioral control was triggered by belief controlling that's s strong perception and the possibility of hinder and facilitate factors on behavior (Johe and Bhullar, 2016).

If these factors reflect the accurate truly, perceived customer behavioral control could play an action as a choice from the true behavioral control and provide aids to predict intended behavior (Rahman et al., 2023). Some empirical research showed the perceived customer behavioral control affected sustainable consumption behavior with beneficial ways (Liu et al., 2020). Related traits with positive and negative individual assessment, depend on what is believed will be occurred when doing certain behavior (Ajzen, 1991).

When a person considered the action is beneficial, this could possibly result in such behavior. Specifically, a person will be tending to own a positive attitude if positively evaluated and as a result they will show the huge willingness to do a definite behavior (Huang et al.,2021).

In accordance with the relevant literatures, the attitude is considered as a persistent trait, though attitude is changeable aligned with the obtained information. In the context of green attitude, customer will tend to choose green product when showing constructive attitude related with environment care (Liu et al., 2023a, 2023b). Aligned with this, some precious studies have shown that customer will be more interested in environmental care will also show huge attitude to a green behavior with environment protection (Han, 2021).

Another previous research (Yin et al., 2022; Ding et al., 2023) claimed that the individual, with strong subjective norm, higher perceived customer behavioral control, positive attitude, tend to conduct good behavior.

TPB model was enlarged in the context of various cultures found to have significant increase to predict customer intention to green purchase (Qi and Ploeger, 2019b). Besides the capability to obey the wide behavior coverage, Flexibility of TPB make it possible to input additional predictor variable (Ajzen, 1991). In this study, it is suggested to combine the TPB with theoretical frame to expand its capability to predict customer behavior.

2.2. Self-Determination Theory (SDT)

SDT represented the exhaustive associated motivation, personality, emotional and especial which lied on the premise that human being required psychological nourishment to perform and conduct ideally (Minami et al., 2021). In accordance with SDT, a motivation or inspiration is existed the whole time which covered the wide supporting motivation spectrum, the external and internal motivation.

Characterized as the externa motivation which is not self-determined or controlled, related by behaving with specific goals to avoid punishment or obtaining incentive from the external party (Ryan and Deci, 2000). Prior research commonly showed that the behavior supported by intrinsic or inherent motivation was significantly related with positive outputs compared with the behavior supported by the externa, such as, the rise of duty perseverance, inventiveness and performance (Ryan and Deci, 2020). Deci and Ryan (1985) defined that inherent motivation was related by applying a behavior to achieve self-goal, not external payback.

In accordance with SDT, intrinsic or inherent motivation was based on psychology needs-based which related with self-determination, competency and interconnection (Ryan and Deci, 2017). The requirements for self-determination related with individual apprehension on self-behavior control, capability to pursue values and self-interest, as well as the feeling not motivated to participate. The needs for competency refers to the wish on power or experiences in effort to obtain what expected. The demand for relationship reflected the needs to experience the relationship with others, to love and care and being treated loving and caring

As one of the most important theory in social science interdisciplinary, SDT had been widely used in the study of customer motivation, especially in the study related with green consumption (Liu et al., 2023a, 2023b). besides, SDT and TPB were consolidated to improve the disadvantages of each theory and delivered a holistic narration in human traits (Luqman et al., 2018), due to the TPB identified the mechanism where the motivation constructs form SDT

resulted a future behavior and SDT offered the platform for construct building based on faith from TPB. Based on the analysis above, present study integrated TPB and SDT to proposed a conceptual idea, which is based on autonomy, competency and related, green attitude, intrinsic or inherent motivation, subjective norms, friendly purchase intension and behavior.

3. HYPOTHESES DEVELOPMENT

3.1. Relationship Between Intrinsic Motivation & Consumers' Green Purchasing Intention

The intrinsic or inherent motivation is the external factor which motivate individual to get engage in an activity due to the satisfaction or self fulfilment obtained from related activity. Meanwhile, customer purchase intention is the wish or customers' tendency to purchase a product or service.

The relationship between intrinsic and purchase intension could be explained through some factors, such as, firstly self-satisfaction, user experiences, value and self-needed, emotional bounding, psychological satisfaction. Intrinsic motivation is often related with the sense of independency and control and consistency with identity. Customers who perceived the purchase is aligned with self-control and independency, they will tend to have purchase intension.

It is important to record that, the correlation between intrinsic motivation and customer GPI could be varied depend on the type of product and service, purchase context as well as customer traits. Firms should notice these factors to be able to develop effective strategic development to attract and sustain customers. Some more recent studies regarding on intrinsic motivation on GPI are worth to mention such as green intrinsic motivation (Ali et al., 2020), Mindfulness and green purchase intention (Daniel et al., 2023), investigating consumers' GPI (Joshi et al., 2021), the investigation of GPI (Wang et al., 2024), green intrinsic and extrinsic motivations interact (Duong et al., 2023).

The need to know what triggers behavior and as individual indicator to willingness behave. Based on TPB, behavior has a strong correlation with the intension when the measurement is conducted on the specific level which is equivalent and relatively small time interval. Green purchase intention described the customer cognitive behavior which designed to choose green product and avoid purchasing product which have negative impact on surrounding (Bhardwaj et al., 2023).

GGPI is generally systematic measured through the intention to purchase eco-friendly product which is at the end could be changed became the decision to purchase the products and promote the environmental sustainability and protection (Han et al., 2022). Thus, it is suggested that green purchase intention could be acted as the indicator as a base of green purchase intention. This is to propose the following hypotheses:

H1: The Higher Level of Customers' Intrinsic Motivation Will Positively Increase Consumers' GPI

3.2. Correlation between Intrinsic Motivation & Green Purchasing Behavior

Intrinsic motivation engaged the internal support to motivate the individual involved in an activity due to the satisfaction and self fulfilment, could have significant impact on purchasing behavior. Some of the interconnected between intrinsic motivation and green purchasing behavior such as choosing products and brands, customer loyalty, customer satisfaction, the impact on purchasing decision, product awareness and knowledge, knowing the importance of purchasing experience, the impact on impulsive purchasing, sustainable purchasing.

The relationship between these variables could be seen from the following study intrinsic motivation and core self-evaluation (Raza et al., 2023), motivational factors and green behaviors (Liaquat et al., 2024), intrinsic motivation with pre-knowledge levels (Stöckert and Bogner, 2021), Pro-environmental attitudes (Corrado et al., 2022), motivations and environmentally responsible behaviors (Kil et al., 2014).

Strong intrinsic motivation could motivate customer to conduct sustainable purchasing from a brand or product by obtaining a satisfaction or self-fulfillment and its sustainability of usage. Intrinsic or inherent motivation could be determined as managing behavior for intrinsic satisfaction, and not for separated outputs, and stimulated individual intrinsically engaged in the duty due to the amusement and intention obtained and consider the feedback as a rewards (Ryan and Deci, 2000).

During the last decade, many authors have highlighted huge attentiveness on the relationship of motivation and GPB (Dong et al., 2022). Though the comprehension of customer motivation to green product purchase is still increased, most of the previous studies described the motivation through extrinsic factors, such as, attitude and subjective norms, and then probed the impact on GPB (Ali et al., 2020).

Furthermore, the extrinsic & extraneous motivation in purchasing emerged form utilitarian purchasing trips, it supported by pleasure and appreciation on shopping experience itself. With the others words, customer will enjoy and appreciate the shopping experience will show the higher motivation to purchase green product. Competing with extrinsic motivation, intrinsic motivation will play huge crucial role during customer purchasing experience (Ryan and Deci, 2020). Thus, by considering the previous study concerned on the impact of intrinsic motivation on GPB, this is to propose the hypothesis as follows

H2: The Higher Level of Customers' Intrinsic Motivation Will Positively Increase Green Purchasing Behavior

3.3. Intrinsic motivation positively affects Environmental attitude

Intrinsic motivation and environmental attitude could affect and contribute on green purchasing behavior. Some factors between intrinsic motivation and environmental attitude, such as value and self-needs, perception on self-responsibility, emotional bounding, the impact of sustainable life style, the needs of self-experience, the satisfaction pro-environment action, education and environmental awareness, acceptance of pro-environmental social norms. Intrinsic motivation could affect how the individual accept the social norm which related with pro-environmental

behavior. Once the intrinsic is strong, the person will tend to adopt social norm which support eco-friendly behavior. The understanding on this relationship could help and design the education program, campaign, or effective environmental initiate by using individual intrinsic motivation to promote green environmental attitude and pro-environmental attitude.

Some previous research regarding on this relationship such as How friendly intrinsic and extrinsic impulse interact, steadiness and imbalance with each other to motivate friendly purchase intention and traits (Duong et al., 2023), green intention-green purchase behavior (Tawde et al., 2023), triggering green behavior (Ahshanul Mamun, 2023), the assessment green purchasing behavior (Wang et al., 2024), key factors affect consumers' behavior (Alyahya et al., 2023), what drives purchase behavior (Le et al., 2023). This is to propose the following hypothesis:

H3: The higher level of customers' Intrinsic motivation will positively increase Environmental attitude

3.4: Green purchasing intention positively affects Environmental attitude

The relationship between green purchase intention and environmental attitude could reflect how far the tendency of customer to buy green product or service. Some factor proved this relationship could be seen from the following, such as purchase intention as attitude expression, the impact of attitude on product selection, customer etiquette consideration, environmental program engagement, an attitude as environment needs drivers, environmental consideration in purchase decision, the needs for environmental brand and label certification.

Eco-friendly attitude could affect the customer perception on brand. Purchase intention could be reflected in supporting the brand which is considered had a strong commitment on environmentally and responsible business practices. The understanding of this relationship could help firms design strategic marketing and product which is aligned with value and customer preferences with environmentally care.

Previous research concerned on this relationship such as green ads increased consumers' purchase intention (Bi et al., 2023), friendly attitude, intention and behaviors lead to friendly purchasing (Trivedi et al., 2018), attitude and purchase intention toward green energy brands (Hartmann and Apaolaza-Ibáñez, 2012), Consumer's intention to purchase 5G (Shah et al., 2021), purchase intention towards environmentally friendly packaged drinks (Meet et al., 2024), Environmental factors affecting green purchase behavior (Ogiemwonyi et al., 2023), environmental awareness and intention on purchase of organic food (Parashar et al., 2023), environmental protection emotion (Lavuri, 2022), consumer attitude on GPI (Zaremohzzabieh et al., 2021), green apparel purchase intention (Pandey and Yadav, 2023). based the aforementioned discussion, current study proposed the following hypothesis:

H4: The higher level of customers' Green purchasing intention will positively increase Environmental attitude.

3.5. The Relationship between GP-Intention positively affects GP-Behavior

The relationship between purchase intention and green purchase behavior reflected how far the customer readiness to translate their intention to be real action in choosing products and services. Some factors showed the strong relationship between these two concepts, such as, conducting purchasing intention, contribution on eco-friendly choice, the influence of environmental attitude on sustainable process, the engagement in sustainable life practices, consideration on environmental impact, support on environmental initiative, the impact of price and quality and participation on re-visit program. Customer who has purchase intention to support sustainable business practices will tend to participate in the revisit program or reuse program. This will reflect the sustainable purchase behavior and take responsibility on environment.

Some previous research concerned on this relationship, such as Determinants of Consumers' Green Purchase Behavior (Yadav and Pathak, 2017), service environment (Wang and Li, 2022), antecedents of Green purchasing behavior (Jaiswal and Kant, 2018), Green" thinking and altruism (Ali et al., 2020). Proposed the following hypothesis:

H5. The higher level of customers' GP-Intention will positively increase GP-Behavior

3.6. Environmental attitude and GP-Behavior

Environmental attitude reflected the evaluation and individual perceived regarding on environment issues. The relation between environmental attitude and **GP-Behavior** and GP-Behavior reflected how far the individual attitude on eco-friendly could support them to adopt sustainable purchasing behavior. Some relationships are seen from the following factors, such as the impact of attitude on product preferences, environmental consideration in purchasing decision.

Sustainable purchasing behavior, supporting on label and environment certification, participation in environmental program, consideration on customer etiquette, the influence of environmental information and customer perception on brand. Positive attitude on environment could increase customer perception on brand. Customer possibly views the brand with good attitude on environment as a better choice and eco-friendly. The understanding on relationship between environmental attitude and green purchase behavior could help firms and marketers to design effective strategic to target customers with high green awareness. This also could support firms to adopt sustainable business practices.

The previous studies related into this relationship such as: Determinants of green behavior (Foukaras and Toma, 2014), environmental attributes (Ramdas and Mohamed, 2014), to integrate common Environmental friendly Knowledge and Eco-Labeling Knowledge (Taufique et al., 2016), Service Environment and Customers' Behavioral Intention (Hashim et al., 2015), friendly product labelling (Miklenčičová, 2015), green Concern, communalism and Ecological Purchase Intention (EPI)(Arisal and Atalar, 2016). Based on TPB, individual attitude is generally affects the behavior. Yet, this relationship is mediated through the

intention. Various studies have shown that customer attitude on environmental was significantly affected the GP-Behavior with GPI as mediating (Cheung and to, 2019).

Specifically, customer’s readiness to pay green electronic was gradually increased, whilst environmental attitude affected the green purchase intention and the rise of awareness to pay eco-friendly products (D’Souza et al., 2020). Others perspectives showed the related correlation of green attitude and GPB had significantly mediated by others factors, such as environmental knowledge and personal norms (Amatulli et al., 2020). Subjective norms played crucial role as behavioral guidance which socially accepted in social group as well as customer which adopt with certain group and often imitated those behavior during decision making.

As a consequence, the support of whole society on green consumption, especially how reference group around customers viewed the green environment behavior, was significantly affected decision making process (Wang et al., 2021). With the others word, subjective norm is possibly become a potential moderator from the role of environment attitude within green purchasing behavior. Inspiring from this discussion, this is to propose the following hypothesis;

H6. The higher level of customers’ Environmental attitude will positively influence green purchasing behavior.

Summarizing the above hypotheses, a grand theoretical model was constructed as illustrated in Fig. 1.

Fig 1: Conceptual Proposed Model

Source: Literature Reviewed (2024)

4. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

4.1. Variables Measurements

To authenticate the latent variable, variable measurement was reviewed through existed robust literatures and paraphrases to align with research regulation, and ensure the reliability and validity are achieved. As illustrated at table 1, intrinsic motivation was measured with 5 scales in accordance with Batat (2020); environment attitude with 5 indicators Xu et a., (2020), meanwhile, the measurement for green purchase intention 5 items Fu et al. (2021), green purchase behavior measured with 4 items Li et al. (2021).

Table 1: Scale Development

Variable	Indicators	Definition	Sources
Intrinsic Motivation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Display genuine passion and enthusiasm • exhibit high levels of persistence • have a sense of autonomy and control • associated with a genuine interest in learning and growing • Lead to sustained and long-term engagement 	Intrinsic Motivation characterized with Display genuine passion and enthusiasm, exhibit high levels of persistence, have a sense of autonomy and control, associated with a genuine or original interest in learning and growing and Lead to sustained and long-term engagement	(Duong et al., 2023, Ali et al., 2020)
Green Purchasing Intention	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Making environmentally conscious purchases • Seek detailed information about the environmental • impact of products Pay attention to the packaging of products • Actively engage in environmentally responsible practices • Members of or actively support environmental organizations 	Green Purchasing Intention is defined by Making environmentally conscious purchases, Seek detailed information about the environmental, impact of products Pay attention to the packaging of products, Actively engage in environmentally responsible practices and Members of or actively support environmental organizations	(Jaiswal and Kant, 2018, Joshi et al., 2021)
Environment Attitude	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • More likely to engage in pro-environmental • Behaviors likely to express about various environmental issues • Likely to support & advocate for Policies & regulations protect • Environment Positive attitudes toward & a preference for sustainable or eco-friendly • Consider the environmental impact of choices when making purchases, planning activities 	Environment Attitude is defined with some trait More likely to engage in pro-environmental, Behaviors likely to express about various environmental issues, Likely to support & advocate for Policies & regulations protect, Environment Positive attitudes toward & a preference for sustainable or eco-friendly and Consider the environmental impact of choices when making purchases, planning activities	(Miklenčičová, 2015, Wang et al., 2024)
Green Purchasing Behavior	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Recognized eco-labels or certifications • Products with eco-friendly packaging • Energy-efficient have a high environmental impact • Prioritize locally sourced & sustainably product 	Green Purchasing Behavior could be defined as recognized eco-labels or certifications, Products with eco-friendly packaging, Energy-efficient have a high environmental impact and Prioritize locally sourced & sustainably product	(Foukaras and Toma, 2014, Yadav and Pathak, 2017)

Source: Literatures Reviewed (2024)

4.2. Data Collecting

The original of items measurement was originally in English and developed in to Bahasa Indonesia. Furthermore, pilot test was conducted with 50 respondents to evaluate the reliability and validity as well as correlation in the conceptual model. Since the output is aligned with rule of thumb, questionnaires were distributed through google firm as well as personal email in to Indonesian customers. The questionnaires with 10 Likert scale where 1 administered strongly disagree, and 10 for strongly agree. To avoid bias potency and research etiquette, green products are defined as a product showed the natural conservation and low pollution, such as

house hold low energy, organic foods and eco-friendly. For data accuracy collected, current research deployed offline survey through google form during September and October 2023 in Indonesia (represented big cities) and aimed at customers who had purchased green products or had experiences eco-friendly products. As many 400 respondents filled and completed the survey but there were 380 questionnaires were valid for further analysis. As many as 101 or 26,58% are male respondents and 279 (79,42%) are female. The ratio 41,31% were represented by the age 41-50 years old, while undergraduate respondents score the highest percentage (60,52). Respondents with monthly income ranged in 5 – 10 million (71,05). For more details, as illustrate at table 2.

Table 2: Participants Demographic profile

Participants Characteristic	Categories	Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	101	26,58
	Female	279	73,42
Age	≤ 20	21	5,80
	21 – 30	50	13,16
	31 – 40	98	25,80
	41 – 50	157	41,31
	51 - 60	54	14,21
	> 61	-	
Education Background	Senior High	10	2,6
	Diploma	80	21,05
	Undergraduate	230	60,52
	Post-Graduate above	60	15,80
Monthly Income	≤ 5.000.000,-	14	3,70
	5.000.100 – 10.000.000	276	71,05
	> 10.000.000	90	23,70

Source: Data Analyzed (2024)

4.3. Research Method

Since the assumption among predictor variables are complicated. Current research deployed SEM-AMOS to test hypotheses accurately. As new path analysis which provide the tools to explore observed latent variables. SEM with AMOS covered comprehensive framework to evaluate variables with many aspects, mainly complicated hypotheses with many path relationship, in the context of multivariate data analysis (Hair and Alamer, 2022).

5. RESULT

Current research deployed SEM-AMOS 24 with two steps analysis such as evaluating the reliability and extensive measurement validity and in accordance with by hypotheses assessment.

5.1. Measurement Model

The steadiness of internal model was estimated by Cronbach’s alpha (CA) and Composite Reliability (CR). As illustrated in table 3 CA and CR are shown high internal consistency above

0,70 (Hair., 2021). All loading factors are bigger than 0,70 (Hair et al., 2021). Using Extracted Variance Average to measure the convergent validity and shown above 0,50.

Table 3: Investigating of Measurement Model

Constructs	Items	Loadings Factor	Cronbach's α	Composite Reliability	AVE
Intrinsic Motivation	Display Genuine Passion & Enthusiasm	0,85	0,74	0,80	0,68
	Exhibit High Levels of Persistence	0,85			
	Have A Sense of Autonomy & Control	0,68			
	Associated With A Genuine Interest In Learning & Growing	0,69			
	Lead to Sustained & Long-Term Engagement	0,67			
Green Purchasing Intention	Making Environmentally Conscious Purchases	0,75	0,71	0,78	0,62
	Seek Detailed Information About The Environmental	0,71			
	Impact of Products Pay Attention to The Packaging of Products	0,76			
	Actively Engage In Environmentally Responsible Practices	0,69			
	Members of Actively Support Environmental Organizations	0,66			
Environment Attitude	More Likely to Engage In Pro-Environmental Behaviors Likely to Express About Various Environmental Issues	0,58	0,70	0,76	0,60
	Likely to Support & Advocate For Policies & Regulations Protect	0,76			
	Environment Positive Attitudes Toward & A Preference For Sustainable or Eco-Friendly	0,83			
	Consider The Environmental Impact of Choices When Making Purchases, Planning Activities	0,69			
Green Purchasing Behavior	Recognized Eco-Labels or Certifications	0,76	0,76	0,84	0,78
	Products With Eco-Friendly Packaging	0,79			
	Energy-Efficient Have A High Environmental Impact	0,79			
	Prioritize Locally Sourced & Sustainably Product	0,73			

Source: Output SEM-AMOS 22 (2024)

Measuring the discriminant validity, Heterotrait Monotrait (HTMT) ratio and criteria were used Fornell and Larcker (1981). Fornell & Larcker (1981), each contract required to show strong correlation with its own construct contrasted with others construct for discriminant validity-DV. Table 4 illustrated the diagonal items, the square root of the AVE among constructs and measurements, it is bigger than if compared with non-diagonal items, that's is the relationship among constructs, showed the strong discriminant. While the value of HTMT also showed reliability under 0,85 (Sarstedt et al., 2019). In accordance with the aforementioned analysis, model analysis showing reliability and convergent validity & sufficient discriminant validity.

Table 4: The Measurements' Discriminant Validity

Construct	Intrinsic Motivation	Green Purchase Intention	Environment Attitude	Green Purchase Behavior
Intrinsic Motivation	0,80			
GPI	0,76	0,83		
Environment Attitude	0,72	0,77	0,80	
GPB	0,70	0,72	0,66	0,85
HTMT Criterion	Intrinsic Motivation	Green Purchase Intention	Environment Attitude	Green Purchase Behavior
Intrinsic Motivation	0,60			
GPI	0,66	0,53		
Environment Attitude	0,62	0,67	0,50	
GPB	0,50	0,62	0,46	0,45

Source: Statistical Output (2024)

5.2. Full Structural Model

Current model proposed four variables, intrinsic motivation, green purchasing intention and environment attitude as the antecedents of green purchase behavior (consequences). chi-square sow 218,64 with df 146. P (0,000), CMIN/DF (1,498). Goodness Fit of Index (0,944) showing a very fit index, AGFI (0,926), TLI (o,973), CFI (0,977), RMSEA (0,36) and HOELTER (330). For more details, as seen at the following Fig 2.

Fig 2: Full Structural Model

Source: Statistical Output SEM-AMOS 22 (2024)

5.2. Full Structural Model

This study proposed six hypotheses, based on statistical output, the highest CR (6,283) the impact of IM on GPI as H1 is accepted. Secondly, CR (5,0), the high level of GPI will influence EA as H4 is also accepted. Thirdly, CR (5,822), the high level of IM will influence the EA (H3 is accepted). Fourthly, the high level of EA will affect the GPB (H5 is accepted). IM will influence GPB as H2 accepted. And finally the high level of GPI will also increase GPB as H6 is accepted.

Table 5: Path Assessment deploying Maximum Likelihood Estimates

Hypotheses		Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P	Label
GPI	<--- Intrinsic Motivation	,401	,064	6,283	***	par_21
Environmental Attitude	<--- GPI	,299	,060	5,011	***	par_16
Environmental Attitude	<--- Intrinsic Motivation	,363	,062	5,822	***	par_20
GPB	<--- Intrinsic Motivation	,194	,077	2,515	,012	par_17
GPB	<--- Environmental Attitude	,467	,090	5,170	***	par_18
Green Purchasing Behavior	<--- GPI	,161	,075	2,134	,033	par_19

Source: Statistical Output SEM-AMOS 22 (2024)

6. DISCUSSION

6.1. Conclusion

Current study investigated the determinant factors of Green customer's purchase Behavior by deploying the frame work of TPB which is combined with SDT and found that GP-Behavior was directly affected by green purchase intention, environment attitude, and intrinsic motivation. Green customer's behavior was affected positively by GPI as aligned with (Roh et al., 2022).

Besides, the customer intrinsic motivation also proven as the antecedent of GCB Lin (2023). Environmental attitude was positively affected the GPB, the consistency with the previous study (Joshi et al., 2020). As a consequence, this finding was validated that GPI which reflected by customers acted as the effective indicator for green customer purchase behavior and aligned with the previous study (Shehawy, 2023).

6.2. Implications

6.2.1. Theoretical implications

Research findings are contributed on literatures. Firstly, in the initial effort to increase the implementation of TPB model was used to measure the GPI with eco-friendly attitude as a key factors of potential customer green purchase. By integrating the SDT and TPB to exploit customer motivation to purchase friendly product, which still considered low exploration from

the previous research related with green customer purchase behavior (Bhardwaj et al., 2023) and highlighted that motivation the most key to trigger customer intention and environmental attitude. By investigating that, it will be expecting to enrich research which merely analyzed the latent variable to investigate GPI (Sun., 2022).

Comparing with the previous research concerned on green consumption which consider the subjective norm is a determinant of GPI (Roh., 2022), and this study considered that subjective norm innovates as the moderating variable.

The empirical finding showed that subjective norm could fill the gap between attitude and behavior and offered a new understanding regarding on green purchase behavior. Indonesia a devolving countries, as a sample to explore customer behavior. Thus, this finding function as useful supplement for existed literatures which focused on develop and other developing countries (Jaiswal and Kant, 2018).

The geographic shifting in field of this study enables us to obtain the unique ideas regarding on the determinant factors of GPB in the context of culture, different economic and social.

6.2.2. Practical implications

Present study contributed in some aspects. The finding on positive impact from green customer intention which is affected by basic psychology, such as green intention offered some practical implications for firms to be able to formulate the strong marketing strategic and support the market for green product.

Specifically, related firms able to take an action to fulfill customer basic needs on green products and facilitate customer purchase decision making on green product. The intrinsic motivation revealed as the key determinant factor to trigger the green customer purchase behavior.

This could offer firms some new insights regarding on marketing campaign. Firm could build physic experience shop to experience superior green on potential customers, this designed to strengthen the intrinsic satisfaction, the motivation and intention on green purchase.

6.3. Limitations & Future Research

Though own the theoretical and practical implication, generally, the study has limitation. This study was based on statistical study and cross-sectional data which collected possibly limits the related causal.

Thus, longitudinal and experimental design are needed to investigate the green customer intention and behavior between explained variable and explored, such EA and GCSB.

This study only assessed several factor's roles in GPB. Thus, future research should consider some other constructs such as social media marketing (Zafar et al., 2021), knowledge on green product, which is well known GPK (Dong et al., 2022) as well as green product quality (Bhardwaj et al., 2023), to build the more comprehensive model which enables to show a better causal relationship concerned on green customer purchase behavior.

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